

Book *of* Abstracts

SPHERIC25

19th SPHERIC World Conference

Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya UPC–BarcelonaTech
17-19 June 2025

Escola de Camins

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Book of Abstracts of the 19th SPHERIC World Conference

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Dr. Corrado Altomare

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From Bastaixos to Researchers: building for the common good

*In 14th-century Barcelona, humble port workers known as **bastaixos** voluntarily carried heavy stones from Montjuïc to help build Santa Maria del Mar church. They did it not for fame or fortune, but as a **gift to their community**—a silent act of dedication that still stands today.*

Centuries later, that same spirit lives on in the work of those who advance knowledge and innovation—whether in universities, research centres, public institutions, or industry. Though we no longer carry stones, we carry ideas. We dedicate ourselves—often behind the scenes—to develop new tools, simulate complex phenomena, design safer systems, and improve the world around us.

*Like the bastaixos, our mission is **service**. Not to build cathedrals, but to build understanding.*

*Because true progress, then and now, is **built collectively**—stone by stone, idea by idea.*

Foreword to the 19th SPHERIC World Conference

Dear Delegate,

The Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya – BarcelonaTech and the Barcelona Supercomputing Centre were honoured to host the **19th SPHERIC World Conference** in the vibrant city of Barcelona (Spain). The event stood as the foremost international forum of 2025 dedicated to **Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH)**, bringing together researchers and practitioners to share insights, foster collaboration, and chart the future of SPH across science and industry.

SPHERIC (SPH rEsearch and engineeRing International Community) represents the dynamic, global network of SPH users. As a fully Lagrangian, meshless technique, SPH enabled the simulation of highly complex phenomena—free-surface flows, multiphase interactions, large deformations in solids, fluid–structure interaction, and more—addressing scenarios where conventional Eulerian methods often fell short.

The conference provided the global platform exclusively devoted to SPH. Leading experts delivered talks spanning theoretical advances, numerical techniques, software development, experimental validation, and real-world applications.

This edition introduced several important innovations: traditional abstracts and proceedings were replaced by **extended abstracts**, allowing authors to present their work with greater clarity and detail, and a **Special Issue** in Computational Particle Mechanics was launched, offering a high-impact platform for selected contributions.

One of the highlights was the debut of **Special Sessions**, each curated by experts to focus on emerging and high-impact SPH applications. The session on **SPH in Aerospace and Maritime Fields**, organized by Salvatore Marrone and PengNan Sun, focused on topics like sloshing in aircraft and ships, and aircraft ditching. Led by Tom De Vuyst, **Solids Mechanics** offered a compelling selection of works exploring high-strain scenarios, complex boundary conditions, and new numerical approaches for structural materials. The session on **SPH Application in Coastal Engineering**, organized by Tomohiro Suzuki, explored wave dynamics and the complex interactions between multiple bodies and sea waves in the context of coastal protection. Finally, the session on **Renewable Energy Engineering Innovations through SPH Modeling**, convened by Alejandro J. C. Crespo and Bonaventura Tagliaferro, showcased works on floating offshore wind turbines, wave energy converters, hydraulic turbines, and other renewable systems, culminating in a lively panel discussion.

It was a pleasure to welcome you and witness the continued expansion of the SPHERIC community. We sincerely thank all participants for their intellectual contributions, enthusiasm, and engagement, which made this conference a resounding success.

With gratitude,

Corrado Altomare

Chair of the Local Organizing Committee of the 19th SPHERIC World Conference

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Table of contents

Session 1: CONVERGENCE, CONSISTENCY AND STABILITY (I)	1
Talk 1.1: How to train your IMP (Implicit Mid-Point) <i>D. Duque, J. Calderon-Sanchez, J. L. Cercós-Pita, P. Eleazar-Merino</i>	
Talk 1.2: Development of Fluid Interphase Particle for particle-based multiphase flow simulation <i>N. Tsuruta, T. Gotoh, A. Khayyer, H. Gotoh</i>	
Talk 1.3: Towards h/p refinement for Weakly Compressible SPH obtained with Eulerian/Lagrangian coupling <i>F. Ricci, R. Vacondio, G. Fourtakas</i>	
Talk 1.4: δ -SPH Stabilization For ISPH Scheme <i>M. De Leffe, C. Hermange, A. Bourgoin, L. Chiron</i>	
Session 2: SOLIDS MECHANICS (SS2)	13
Talk 2.1: A first-order conservation law framework for large strain compressible solids: isothermal viscoelasticity <i>C. Hean Lee, T. Jaugielavičius, S. Boyaval, A. J. Gil, J. Bonet, D. Violeau</i>	
Talk 2.2: An enhanced SPH-based hydroelastic FSI solver with structural dynamic hourglass control <i>Y. Zhan, M. Luo, A. Khayyer</i>	
Talk 2.3: Advancing the Material Point Method for Brittle Shells in Computational Mechanics <i>M. Stilz, G. Ganzenmüller, S. Hiermaier</i>	
Session 3: HIGH-PERFORMANCE COMPUTING	21
Talk 3.1: Towards heterogeneous parallelism for SPHinXsys <i>X. Hu, A. Guarnieri</i>	
Talk 3.2: TNL-SPH: Open-source modular SPH solver for modern distributed computing platforms based on GPU accelerators <i>T. Halada, L. Beneš, J. Klinkovský, T. Oberhuber</i>	
Talk 3.3: GPU acceleration of SWIFT for heterogeneous Exascale supercomputers <i>A. Nasar, G. Fourtakas, S. Kay, B. D. Rogers, M. Schaller</i>	
Session 4: RIEMANN SOLVERS	30
Talk 4.1: Riemann based SPH with divergence cleaning <i>G. Fourtakas, R. Vacondio</i>	
Talk 4.2: A Coefficient-Free β -Velocity Formulation for Improved Riemann-Based SPH <i>M. A. Hafeez, R. Vacondio, A. English, B. D. Rogers, G. Fourtakas</i>	
Talk 4.3: An enhanced coupled ISPH-TLSPH FSI solver by a Riemann fluid-structure acceleration scheme <i>T. Gotoh, A. Khayyer, H. Gotoh</i>	
Talk 4.4: SPH modelling of water flow inside a porous medium using a Riemann based formulation <i>C. D. Sousa, G. Oger, J. Michel, D. L. Touzé, D. Violeau</i>	
Session 5: COUPLING WITH OTHER METHODS	42
Talk 5.1: Coupling of SPH and Volume-of-Fluid <i>M. Wicker, N. Bürkle, R. Koch, H. J. Bauer</i>	
Talk 5.2: A two-way ISPH-FVM coupling for two-phase flows <i>M. Helal, M. S. Shadloo, V. Moureau, M. Cailler</i>	
Talk 5.3: A coupled WCSPH-MSDEM model for combined motion of a block contact with solid-wall boundary <i>S. Gao, B. Ren, H. Wen</i>	

Talk 5.4: A coupled FV-SPH approach to simulate the flow around a vertical free-surface piercing cylinder

S. Marrone, A. Colagrossi, A. D. Mascio, D. L. Touzé

Session 6: SPH IN AEROSPACE AND MARITIME FIELDS (SS1-I)

54

Talk 6.1: Numerical simulation of long-term sloshing flows using an enhanced SPH model

M. Luo, Y. Zhan, A. Khayyer

Talk 6.2: Violent sloshing flows with thermal conduction using δ -LES-SPH

A. Colagrossi, S. Marrone, M. Antuono, J. Calderon-Sanchez, L. M. González-Gutierrez

Talk 6.3: A first isothermal approach to 3D sloshing for aircraft hydrogen tanks.

Ignacio Sánchez-Ojeda, J. Calderon-Sanchez, L. M. González-Gutierrez

Talk 6.4: A versatile SPH algorithm for multiphase pipe flow

Z. Y. Zhan, Z. Chen

Session 7

Track A: CONVERGENCE, CONSISTENCY AND STABILITY (II)

66

Talk 7.1A: Towards high-order simulation of compressible flows: insights from dispersion analysis

O.P. Stoyanovskaya, M.S. Arendarenko, O.A. Burmistrova, V.V. Grigoryev, T.V. Markelova

Talk 7.2A: Investigation on the accuracy and numerical dissipation when using the ULPH model for free-surface flows

S. X. Wu, P. N. Sun, X. T. Huang

Talk 7.3A: Pairing instability: insights and possible remedies from a local thermodynamics perspective

G. Colella, J. B. Avalos, J. P. Larentzos

Talk 7.4A: A new classification and convergence study of sph-like first and second spatial derivatives schemes

R. Fatehi

Track B: INDUSTRIAL APPLICATIONS IN HYDRAULICS

78

Talk 7.1B: SPH-Based Fluid-Structure Interaction to Aid Rapid Prototyping for Vehicle Water Wading

M. Make, A. Peer, S. Joshi

Talk 7.2B: Investigation of Reducing Metalworking Fluid Consumption in Deep-Hole Drilling using Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics

A. Baumann, P. Eberhard

Talk 7.3B: Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics Simulation of 3D Open Channel Flow Over Vegetated Bed

E. Chatzoglou, A. Liakopoulos

Talk 7.4B: SPH modeling for plastic transport in the nearshore zone: a laboratory-scale validation study

R. Cristofaro, A. Cappello, G. Ganci, G. Bilotta, C. Iuppa, C. Faraci

Session 8

Track A: RENEWABLE ENERGY ENGINEERING INNOVATIONS THROUGH SPH MODELING (SS4-I)

90

Talk 8.1A: A comparative study on Pelton turbines with CFD-based methods

A. Ferrarini, R. Bergamin, M. Merelli, M. Galbiati, J. M. Domínguez

Talk 8.2A: SPH chamber model towards pneumatic PTO representation for floating OWC devices

B. Mina, B. Tagliaferro, I. Martínez-Estévez, G. Malara, F. Arena, M. Gómez-Gesteira

Talk 8.3A: SPH analysis of extreme wave directionality on the dynamics of floating offshore wind turbines

S. Wang, W. L. Chuang

Talk 8.4A: Application of the SPH method to simulate coupled ionic transport and electrodeposition in lithium batteries <i>M. Morey, E. Ryan</i>	
Track B: BIOMEDICAL AND NON NEWTONIAN FLOWS	102
Talk 8.1B: SPH-Based FSI Simulations of Blood Flow in Patient-Specific Vessels with Deformable Walls <i>C. Zhao, O. J. Haidn, D. Wu, X. Hu</i>	
Talk 8.2B: Compared SPH and LBM approaches for FSI of trans-aortic flows <i>J. Lopez, M. Lallemand, J. Michel, D. L. Touzé, G. Oger</i>	
Talk 8.3B: LHMM for Rheological Analysis of Polymer Melts with DPD-SPH Coupling <i>E. A. Patiño-Nariño, N. Moreno, M. Ellero</i>	
Talk 8.4B: Coupled SPH Model for Prosthetic Valve Induced Thrombus Formation <i>S. Laha, G. Fourtakas, P. K. Das, A. Keshmiri</i>	
Session 9	
Track A: ASTROPHYSICS	114
Talk 9.1A: Protoplanetary Disc Evolution in Binary Systems: A Combined SPH and Radiative Transfer Study <i>P. P. Poblete</i>	
Talk 9.2A: In-Situ Visualization and Analysis for SPH Simulations <i>J. M. Favre, J. G. Piccinali, R. Cabezón</i>	
Talk 9.3A: Semi-confined supernovae in Giant Molecular Clouds and their impact on the interstellar medium <i>C. S. C. Lau, I. A. Bonnell</i>	
Track B: SPH IN AEROSPACE AND MARITIME FIELDS (SS1-II)	121
Talk 9.1B: Towards High-Fidelity Simulation of Compressible Flows Using Adaptive Resolution SPH <i>N. Villodi, P. Ramachandran</i>	
Talk 9.2B: SPH-based modelling of ships and ocean platforms operating in extreme environments <i>M. S. Islam</i>	
Talk 9.3B: Simulation of ship dynamics and structural response based on SPH <i>C. Ma, M. Oka</i>	
Session 10: BOUNDARY CONDITIONS	130
Talk 10.1: Pair-particle dispersion in two dimensional SPH <i>D.D. Meringolo, S. Servidio, C. Meringolo, F. Aristodemo, P.G.F. Filianoti, P. Veltri, V. Carbone</i>	
Talk 10.2: On the consistency of the SPH gradient with a Boundary Integral Method for solid wall modelling <i>V. Degand, J. Michel, D. L. Touzé, G. Oger</i>	
Talk 10.3: Wall boundary condition for the unconditionally stable SPH <i>J. L. Cercós-Pita, P. Eleazar-Merino, D. Duque, J. Calderón-Sánchez</i>	
Talk 10.4: Towards oscillation-free spectral ISPH scheme with high-order wall boundary conditions <i>M. Lin, G. Fourtakas, B. D. Rogers</i>	
Session 11	
Track A: SPH APPLICATION IN COASTAL ENGINEERING (SS3-I)	142
Talk 11.1A: SPH modelling of submarine debris flow and turbidity currents transition and FSI processes <i>D. Feng, C. Yi</i>	

Talk 11.2A: Enhancing breaking wave impact predictions on vertical piles: about the influence of dissipation terms in SPH momentum equation

C. Altomare, Y. P. Li

Talk 11.3A: An enhanced inlet boundary condition for stable and accurate nonlinear wave simulations

T. Kanehira, S. Draycott, B. D. Rogers, P. Stansby

Talk 11.4A: A generalized boundary condition for generating wave–current coupling flows in a 3D numerical tank

H. G. Lyu, P. N. Sun

Track B: ADVANCED NUMERICAL STRATEGIES FOR FREE SURFACE FLOWS **154**

Talk 11.1B: Application of Localized Implicit Iterative Particle Shifting on Free Surface Flows

M. A. Ghazi, R. Vacondio, J. C. Marongiu

Talk 11.2B: – A high accurate meshless method for free surface flows

J. M. Ortiz de Urbina, L. Ramírez

Talk 11.3B: The pressure signal in simulations of weakly compressible SPH

G. Lipari

Talk 11.4B: Framework for uncertainty quantification of wave-structure interaction in a flume

X. Luo, A. Revell, G. Fourtakas, A. B. Harish

Session 12

Track A: SPH APPLICATION IN COASTAL ENGINEERING (SS3-II) **166**

Talk 12.1A: Constrained fluid-debris impacts onto non-rigid structures in extreme hydrodynamic events using DUALSPHYSICS+CHRONO

G. Ruffini, P. D. Girolano, R. Briganti, A. D. Iasio, N. Goseberg, J. Stolle, I. Martínez-Estévez, B. Ghiassi

Talk 12.2A: Stability of tetrapod mound breakwaters against solitary waves using the SPH method

I. Martínez-Estévez, A.J.C. Crespo, J.M. Domínguez, M. Gómez-Gesteira, B. Tagliaferro, T. Suzuki, C. Altomare, S. Capasso, W. Suwannarat, J. Mitsui, S. Kubota

Talk 12.3A: Comparative Analysis of 3D Flood Dynamics under Extreme Wave Overtopping Conditions Using Lagrangian and Eulerian Approaches

J. Yoo, G. Jeong, B. Kim

Talk 12.4A: Extending the Frontiers of Coastal Engineering: Real-World Applications of DualSPHysics to Breakwaters and Quays

A. Marzeddu, C. Altomare

Track B: MACHINE LEARNING **178**

Talk 12.1B: Can Machine Learning Bridge the Gap Between Lagrangian Mesh-Free Methods and High-Order Interpolants?

L. G. Starepravo, J. King, G. Fourtakas, A. Harish, S. Lind

Talk 12.2B: MoriNet: A Machine Learning-based Mori-Zwanzig Perspective on Weakly Compressible SPH

R. Winchenbach, N. Thuerey

Talk 12.3B: Autoencoders for Lagrangian Computational Fluid Dynamics

J. O' Connor

Session 13

Track A: SPH IN AEROSPACE AND MARITIME FIELDS (SS1-III) **187**

Talk 13.1A: Rapid Variable Resolution Particle Initialization for Complex Geometries

N. Villodi and P. Ramachandran

Talk 13.2A: An efficient SPH model for the simulation of water-dropping from airtankers

X. S. Guan, P. N. Sun, X. T. Huang

Talk 13.3A: A nesting strategy to model a propeller jet wake on a scoured bathymetry using SPH

D. Ferraro, R. Gaudio, F. Aristodemo, J. M. Domínguez, A. Lauria, C. Altomare

Track B: Renewable Energy Engineering Innovations through SPH Modeling (SS4-II)

196

Talk 13.1B: Design of a Generic Chrono Framework for Fluid-Solid Interaction

R. Serban, L. Bakke, H. Unjhwala, D. Negrut

Talk 13.2B: A design tool for flexible wave energy converters based on SPH

S. Capasso, I. Martínez-Estévez, M. Göteman, J. M. Domínguez, M. Gómez-Gesteira, C. Altomare, G. Viccione, A. J. C. Crespo

Talk 13.3B: DualSPHysics validation for fluid-structure interaction with floating flexible structure in a sloshing tank environment

F. Bernardo, M. Brito, R. M.L. Ferreira, J. Leal, I. Martínez-Estévez

Session 14: SURFACE TENSION, VISCOSITY AND TURBULENCE

205

Talk 14.1: Drop coalescence and break-up through the RHOD-SPH

M. Antuono, S. Marrone, A. Colagrossi

Talk 14.2: A multi-physics single-phase SPH scheme to simulate droplet migration on a heated solid surface

C. Cen, G. Fourtakas, B. D. Rogers, S. J. Lind, A. English

Talk 14.3: Investigation of wall functions in SPH for turbulent flow modelling

A. English, R. Vacondio

Talk 14.4: Capturing violent and turbulent sloshing dynamics using SPH modelling

C. Pilloton, A. Colagrossi, H. G. Lyu, P. N. Sun

Session 15: ADAPTIVITY

217

Talk 15.1: Adaptive particle refinement for compressible smoothed particle hydrodynamics

D. J. Price, R. Nealon

Talk 15.2: Extension of the RHOD-SPH framework: towards a fully Adaptive Particle Refinement technique

J. Michel, G. Oger, S. Marrone, A. Colagrossi, D. Le Touzé

Talk 15.3: Variable resolution SPH with a Local Time Stepping procedure

F. Ricci, R. Vacondio, A. Tafuni

DROP COALESCENCE AND BREAK-UP THROUGH THE RHOD-SPH

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I. INTRODUCTION

The present paper is dedicated to the study of coalescence and break-up phenomena of viscous drops with surface tension. The fluid is assumed to be Newtonian and, therefore, is described through the Navier-Stokes equations (NSEs). The work is carried on through the use of the RHOD-SPH scheme defined in [1] (we address the reader to this paper for details on the numerical model) and relies on the analysis of the energy balance during the above-mentioned phenomena.

Hereinafter, we disregard the presence of solid boundaries and assume that the boundary is a free surface, namely $\Omega = \Omega_F$. Hence, the energy equation of the NSEs is:

$$\frac{D}{Dt} \int_{\Omega} \rho_0 \frac{\|\mathbf{u}\|^2}{2} dV = \sigma \int_{\partial\Omega_F} \kappa (\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{n}) dS - 2\mu \int_{\Omega} \mathbb{D} : \mathbb{D} dV \quad (1)$$

where σ is the surface tension and κ is the curvature of the free surface. It is possible to show that the integral related to the surface tensions is equivalent to the material derivative of the surface area, namely:

$$\int_{\partial\Omega_F} \kappa (\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{n}) dS = -\frac{D}{Dt} \left(\int_{\partial\Omega_F} dS \right) \quad (2)$$

This allows one to rearrange the energy equation in the following compact form:

$$\frac{D\mathcal{E}_K}{Dt} + \frac{D\mathcal{E}_\sigma}{Dt} = \mathcal{P}_v \quad (3)$$

where \mathcal{E}_K is the kinetic energy, $\mathcal{E}_\sigma = \sigma \mathcal{L}_F$ is the surface tension energy (here \mathcal{L}_F is the free-surface area) and, finally, \mathcal{P}_v indicates dissipated by viscous effects. Since we do not consider external forcing terms, the flows studied in the present work only depends on the Reynolds and Weber numbers defined as:

$$\text{Re} = \frac{\rho_0 U_{ref} L}{\mu}, \quad \text{We} = \frac{\rho_0 U_{ref}^2 L}{\sigma}$$

where U_{ref} and L are the reference velocity and length of the problem at hand respectively.

A. The surface-tension model

The Continuum Surface Force (CSF) model described in [2] has been implemented in the RHOD-SPH scheme. In particular, the surface tension force \mathbf{F}_i^σ is given below:

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{F}_i^\sigma &= \sigma \kappa_i \mathbf{n}_i \delta_{Fi}, & \delta_{Fi} = 2 \left\| \sum_j \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \right\| \\ \kappa_i &= \mathbb{L}_i \sum_j (\mathbf{n}_i - \mathbf{n}_j) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j, & \mathbf{n}_i = -\frac{\nabla \lambda_i}{\|\nabla \lambda_i\|}, \\ \nabla \lambda_i &= \mathbb{L}_i \sum_j (\lambda_j - \lambda_i) \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j, \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where λ_i is the minimum eigenvalue of \mathbb{L}_i^{-1} and \mathbb{L}_i is the renormalization matrix. As in [2], four critical corrections necessary for the description of thin jets or small drops are also implemented in order to increase accuracy and robustness of the scheme. The above scheme has been further validated in [3], proving to be robust and accurate.

B. Energy balance of the RHOD-SPH model

The energy balance of the RHOD-SPH model is rather complex because of the presence of power terms related to the use of the shifting velocity and Riemann fluxes. In the present work, however, we mainly focus on the action played by the surface tension force. Hence, for this reason and for the ease of the treatise, some of the remaining terms of the energy equation are introduced without giving their whole expressions. In any case, more details can be found in [1].

The energy balance of the particle system can be rewritten as:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{D\mathcal{E}_K}{Dt} + \frac{D\mathcal{E}_C}{Dt} = \mathcal{P}_{diss} + \mathcal{P}_\sigma, & \mathcal{E}_K = \sum_i m_i \frac{\|\mathbf{u}_i\|^2}{2}, \\ \mathcal{E}_C = \sum_i m_i \int_{\rho_0}^{\rho_i} \frac{p(s)}{s^2} ds, & \mathcal{P}_\sigma = \sum_i (\mathbf{F}_i^\sigma \cdot \mathbf{u}_i), \\ \mathcal{P}_v = \sum_i (\mathbf{F}_i^\mu \cdot \mathbf{u}_i), & \mathcal{P}_{diss} = \mathcal{P}_v + \mathcal{P}_N, \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where \mathcal{E}_C is the (reversible) energy associated with the fluid compressibility, \mathcal{P}_σ is the power of the surface tension force, \mathcal{P}_v is the power dissipated by the viscous effects and, finally, \mathcal{P}_N is

the power due to the action of the remaining numerical terms (mainly the particle shifting terms and the Riemann fluxes). In principle, this latter term has not a definite sign, but it always works as a dissipation in the numerical scheme. For this reason, we denote by $\mathcal{P}_{diss} = \mathcal{P}_v + \mathcal{P}_N$ the overall power dissipated by the numerical scheme.

Before proceeding, we introduce the energy dissipated by the RHOD-SPH and the work done by the surface tension force as:

$$Q_{diss} = \int_{t_0}^t \mathcal{P}_{diss} d\tau, \quad \mathcal{W}_\sigma = \int_{t_0}^t \mathcal{P}_\sigma d\tau. \quad (6)$$

According to the equation (2), \mathcal{P}_σ should be equal to $(-D\mathcal{E}_\sigma/Dt)$ and, consequently, \mathcal{W}_σ should be equal to $(\mathcal{E}_{\sigma 0} - \mathcal{E}_\sigma)$. Nonetheless, this is not true numerically, since the reversibility of \mathcal{W}_σ cannot be guaranteed in the adopted SPH model. In fact, the work \mathcal{W}_σ is intrinsically related to the CSF model which is based on the evaluation of local quantities (like the normal and the curvature of the free-surface), without any direct connection with global quantities, like the surface energy associated to the deformation of $\partial\Omega_F$.

In order to check the numerical error of the SPH scheme in the evaluation of the surface energy, \mathcal{E}_σ is evaluated through a Level-Set function ϕ . The latter is obtained by using the algorithm described in [4] based on the interpolation of the particles set on a Cartesian mesh. When the contour level $\phi = 0$ is extracted, it is possible to evaluate the perimeter of the drop \mathcal{L}_F and, therefore, the surface energy $\mathcal{E}_\sigma = \sigma\mathcal{L}_F$. It is worth noting that the Level-Set function is evaluated during a post-processing stage and for a limited number of time instants. Because of the CPU costs, it is not calculated at runtime for each time iteration.

Thanks to the above approach, at the end of each simulations it is possible to check to what extent the work \mathcal{W}_σ deviates from $(\mathcal{E}_{\sigma 0} - \mathcal{E}_\sigma)$ and if the deviation from the theoretical equality ultimately decreases when the spatial resolution $N = L/\Delta x$ increases. Note that the surface energy \mathcal{E}_σ is always evaluated geometrically through the Level-Set function ϕ , whereas the work of the surface tension forces \mathcal{W}_σ is evaluated from the CSF model that is embedded in the SPH scheme.

About the energy associated with the fluid compressibility, namely \mathcal{E}_C , this maintains small during the evolution as a consequence of the weak-compressibility assumption.

II. COALESCING DROPS

Two circular drops of radius R approaching each other with a constant velocity U_0 are set at an initial distance equal to the kernel radius R_W . The initial surface tension energy of the fluid system is $\mathcal{E}_{\sigma 0} = 2\pi\sigma R$, while its asymptotic value for long times is assumed to be that associated with a single circular drop generated by the merging of the initial drops. Since the latter drop has radius $R_\infty = \sqrt{2}R$, the asymptotic energy of the surface tension is $\mathcal{E}_{\sigma\infty} = \sqrt{2}\pi\sigma R$. and, therefore, the overall variation of surface tension energy is $\Delta\mathcal{E} = (\mathcal{E}_{\sigma 0} - \mathcal{E}_{\sigma\infty}) = 2\pi\sigma R(2 - \sqrt{2})$.

Denoting by M_0 the initial mass of the fluid system, we define the reference velocity of the problem as:

$$U_{ref} = \sqrt{\frac{\Delta\mathcal{E}}{M_0}} = \sqrt{\frac{\sigma(2 - \sqrt{2})}{R}} \quad (7)$$

By definition, this implies $We = (2 - \sqrt{2})$, while the Reynolds number has been set equal to 242. These values correspond, for example, to a water drop of 1 mm radius.

Fig. 1. Coalescing drops: early stages of the evolution for $We = (2 - \sqrt{2})$, $Re = 242$ and spatial resolution $N = 800$. Link Video N°1.

Fig. 2. Energy balance for the coalescing drops. The time history of the term $(\mathcal{E}_\sigma - \mathcal{E}_{\sigma 0})/\Delta\mathcal{E}$ has been shifted upward to match with the term $(-\mathcal{W}_\sigma/\Delta\mathcal{E})$ and show the initial gap caused by the coalescing phenomenon.

Hereinafter, $t_0 = 0.5R_W/U_{ref}$ indicates the theoretical time instant when the drops first touch. During the early stages of the evolution, large velocity values are observed at the extremities of the contact line (top panels of figure (1)). These values slowly decrease while the drops deform but remains localized close to the free surface.

Figure 2 displays the energy balance for the coalescing system. In this figure the time history of the surface tension energy, namely $(\mathcal{E}_\sigma - \mathcal{E}_{\sigma 0})/\Delta\mathcal{E}$, has been moved upward to match with the term $(-\mathcal{W}_\sigma/\Delta\mathcal{E})$. This allows us to highlight the generation of an energy gap at the initial time, i.e. when the drops first touch. In particular, during the early stages of coalescence, part of the free surface is trapped inside the two drop volumes, and two cusps are generated and propagate far from the initial contact point. This dynamics holds up until the

Fig. 3. Pressure evolution for a large amplitude oscillation of a 2D liquid drop. The spatial resolution is $N = R/\Delta r = 400$. Link Video N^o2.

cusps disappear and a smooth surface develops. The length ℓ of the free surface that is incorporated inside the merged volumes leads to the energy gap $\delta\mathcal{E}_\sigma = \sigma \ell$ that is observed at the initial time in the Figure 2. This figure also shows that the total energy of the system, namely \mathcal{E}_{tot} , is conserved during the evolution. Such an energy term is obtained by integrating in time the first expression of the equation (5) and corresponds, in fact, to the summation of all the energy contributions, that is:

$$\mathcal{E}_{tot} = \mathcal{E}_K + \mathcal{E}_C - Q_{diss} - \mathcal{W}_\sigma. \quad (8)$$

Accordingly, \mathcal{E}_{tot} is monitored to check that the errors caused by the numerical time integration are negligible in comparison to the physical energy contributions.

III. BREAK-UP

We consider the case of a drop subjected to a two-mode oscillation of large amplitude, according to the analytical solution described in [5]. In particular we set $a = 1.25R$, $Re = 194$ and $We = 9.38$, which approximately corresponds to a water drop of radius $5.6 \cdot 10^{-5}m$. Figure 3 shows the main stages of the evolution of the oscillation drop for $N = R/\Delta r = 400$. The top right panel displays the maximum elongation of the initial drop in two bumps tied by a thin fluid thread. After this instant, the bumps start moving closer (bottom left panel), while the thread becomes thinner and thinner and eventually breaks (bottom right panel), generating tiny secondary drops and large acoustic waves that propagate inside the fluid bulk. Just before the breaking time the fluid tread is just two-particle thick, that is $2\Delta r = R/200$. After this stage, the two separated drops continue moving closer and, finally, merge.

A more detailed insight is provided by the analysis of the energy balance of the fluid system. This is illustrated in Figure

Fig. 4. Large amplitude oscillation of a 2D liquid drop: Top: long-time evolution of the main energy components for $N = 400$. The letters refer to the panels in Figure 3.

4 where the different energy components are shown. During the early evolution \mathcal{W}_σ and \mathcal{E}_σ show a good agreement. The overall behavior changes, however, when the break-up phenomenon occurs. In this case the work done by the surface tension forces, namely \mathcal{W}_σ , undergoes an abrupt discontinuity (Figure 4). This energy loss corresponds to the energy spent to separate the thin thread between the bumps. Conversely, the signal of the surface tension energy, \mathcal{E}_σ , maintains regular, since the overall length of the fluid system undergoes minor changes.

The opposite behavior is observed during the coalescence stage, that is when the drops reconnect after the break-up in the bottom-right panel of Figure 3. Indeed, the surface tension energy \mathcal{E}_σ experiences a sudden energy loss caused by the free-surface entrapment, in analogy to the dynamics described in Section §II. Conversely, the work \mathcal{W}_σ is less affected by the coalescence phenomenon, even though a larger dissipation is observed after the coalescence stage is completed. Remarkably, we observe that in the subsequent evolution \mathcal{W}_σ and \mathcal{E}_σ match together again, proving that the energy lost by \mathcal{W}_σ during the break-up is approximately equal to the energy lost by \mathcal{E}_σ during the coalescence stage.

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